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Magnet specifications based on optics calculations for ELETTRA. Magnetic and mechanical design including fabrication drawings

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ABSTRACT

Elettra is a 2/2.4 GeV third-generation electron storage ring, located near Trieste, Italy. In view of a substantial increase of the machine performance in terms of brilliance, the so-called Elettra 2.0 upgrade is currently on-going. This upgrade is based on a 6-bends achromat, four dipoles of which having a longitudinally variable field. So far, those dipoles are foreseen to provide a field with a two step profile. The VArIable Dipole for the Elettra Ring (VADER) task, driven by the I.FAST European project, aims at developing a new dipole design based on a trapezoidal shape of the bending radius, which would allow for a further reduction of the horizontal emittance. A prototype of this magnet should be designed by the CIEMAT laboratory and build by KYMA company. This note presents and discusses the new dipole field specification and describes the corresponding

optics optimization that was performed in order to reduce at best the emittance of the Elettra ring. It further describes the magnetic and mechanical design, to be the basis for the magnet fabrication.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

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Executive summary

A new variable dipole magnet was specified for reducing the emittance of the upgraded Elettra ring by a further factor of 2. The magnet follows the design principle of the CLIC DRs variable bend demonstrator, with high peak field in the center of 2.3 T and an hyperbolic increase in the edges. In addition, the low field part includes a transverse gradient of 23 T/m. The new optics design was proved to be robust with respect to DA, after a series of tune, sextupoles and octupole optimization. The specifications although more challenging than the CLC DR demonstrator were all achieved during the magnetic design including a field adjustability and good field quality. The mechanical design is ready for proceeding to the magnet fabrication.

1 Introduction

The present Elettra machine is a third-generation Italian light source, located in Trieste. Operating at two different energies of 2 or 2.4 GeV, Elettra presently delivers electron beams with an emittance ranging from 7 to 10 nm.rad [1]. The Elettra 2.0 upgrade [2] aims mainly at reducing the emittance by at least one order of magnitude, while keeping the geometrical structure almost identical. The current plan for the machine upgrade is based on an enhanced 6-bend achromat (S6BA-E), relying on the use of longitudinal gradient (LG) dipoles to reach a bare horizontal emittance of about 210 pm.rad at 2.4 GeV. The dipolar field of those magnets varies longitudinally in the form two steps, to reach 1.43 T (at 2.4 GeV) at the center. The original Elettra 2.0 lattice is presented in Fig. 1 [3].

Fig. 1 Elettra 2.0 S6BA-E cell. The top plot shows the magnetic layout, with the dipole angles in blue and the quadrupolar gradient in red. The lower plot shows the evolution of the optics function throughout the lattice. The horizontal and vertical β -functions are shown with blue and orange lines respectively. The horizontal and vertical dispersion are shown with solid and dash brown lines respectively.

The Elettra 2.0 ring is composed of twelve times this unit cell. The different long (dispersion free) and short (dispersive) sections are used to installed the Insertion Devices (ID) including different types of wigglers, undulators and super-bends, as well as the four RF cavities.

It has been shown that hyperbolic profiles for the longitudinal evolution of the magnetic field could bring better performances in terms of emittance reach [4]. In that respect, this document describes the different steps taken in order to replace the present LG dipoles by the so-called VADER (VARIABLE Dipole for the Elettra Ring). In a first part, the method used to design the dipole longitudinal and implement it in MAD-X is discussed. Then, we will demonstrate how the VADER were included in the Elettra 2.0 lattice and how the optics were tuned in order to reach the best possible performance. A first non-linear optimization is then presented. In a second part, we report the magnetic design performed by the CIEMAT laboratory. Finally, in a last part, we will implement this real profile in MAD-X [5] and adjust again the lattice in order to obtain the best performance in terms of emittance, dynamic aperture and lifetime. In all those studies, we assume a beam energy of 2.4 GeV. The present Elettra 2.0 is indeed foreseen to operate mostly at this energy. Since the VADER will be a permanent magnet, we need to focus on only one energy.

2 Design of a trapezoidal profile

The design of the longitudinal profile is highly inspired by the work presented in [4] where a longitudinally variable dipole was designed for the CLIC [6] damping rings. The maximum field is reached at the center where consequently the bending radius is minimum. We want to design a trapezoidal profile in bending radius as presented in Fig. 2 [4].

Fig. 2 Schematic view of the bending radius profile for the VADER magnet.

The length of the central constant part in field is denoted L_1 , while the length of the varying part is denoted L_2 . Moreover, the minimum bending radius - reached at the center - is denoted ρ_1 , and the maximum - reached at the edge of the dipole - is denoted ρ_2 . The trapezoidal profile is then given by:

$$\rho(s) = \begin{cases} \rho_1, & 0 < s < L_1 \\ \rho_1 + \frac{(L_1-s)(\rho_1-\rho_2)}{L_2}, & L_1 < s < L_1 + L_2 = L/2 \end{cases}.$$

We can therefore define two ratios in terms of lengths and bending radii as:

$$\lambda = \frac{L_1}{L_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\rho} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2}.$$

The design of the longitudinal profile is then determined using those two parameters and the definition of the bending angle provided by such a profile:

$$\theta_{\text{trap}} = \frac{L(\lambda(\tilde{\rho} - 1) + \tilde{\rho} \ln \tilde{\rho})}{\rho_1(\tilde{\rho} - 1)(1 + \lambda)}.$$

Since the peak field of the dipole (2.3 T at 2.4 GeV), the total length L of 0.8 m and the dipole bending angle are determined by the original lattice and the technological constraints, we can choose λ and $\tilde{\rho}$ in order to optimize the emittance reduction. To do so, one can compute the emittance given by a Theoretical Minimum Emittance (TME) cell with a uniform dipole, and the one obtained with a trapezoidal profile. The emittance reduction factor, denoted F_{TME} , is then defined as:

$$F_{TME} = \frac{\varepsilon_{TME, \text{uni}}}{\varepsilon_{TME, \text{trap}}},$$

and the full expression can be found in the Appendix C of [4]. One can then parameterize the emittance reduction factor with λ and $\tilde{\rho}$, for combinations that conserve the magnet bending angle, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Emittance reduction factor F_{TME} as a function of the VADER profile parameters.

The best emittance reduction factor is found for $\lambda = 0.074$ and $\tilde{\rho} = 0.24$. Those parameters are then used to obtain the ideal longitudinal profile of the VADER dipole, as displayed in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Proposal for the ideal VADER longitudinal field profile. The blue line shows the analytical solution, while the red steps show the implementation in MAD-X.

The MAD-X software does not allow the implementation of a continuous longitudinal profile for a dipole. For that reason, it has been chose to split each half-dipole in ten different slices. The varying part of the dipole is sliced in nine, all of the slices having the same length and different bending angle. This is shown with the red lines in Fig. 4.

Once this profile is designed and implemented in MAD-X, one can replace the LG dipoles installed in the original Elettra lattice by those new VADER ones. We can then study the optics in the new lattice, and this is reported in the next section. In the following, we assume that no ID is installed in the machine.

3 Optics design for the new Elettra 2.0 ring

In this study, we strictly keep the original geometrical lattice. Therefore, all dipolar and quadrupolar elements remain at their location. The LG dipoles are replaced by VADER ones. In order to control the dispersion in the long straight sections, a knob is implemented in MAD-X, linking the angle of the external dipoles (the ones located on the outer part of the cell) with the angle of the so-called anti-bends (misaligned quadrupoles creating a negative dipolar angle by feed-down) so that the total bending angle of the cell remains the same. The location of the sextupoles (presently considered thin) has been slightly shifted in order to optimize the chromaticity correction. Moreover, the lattice is matched in order to meet the constraints of the Elettra ring. Namely, our main concern is to ensure the absence of dispersion in the long straight sections while keeping the optics functions at a reasonable level throughout the lattice so that no aperture limit is met. Furthermore, we also match the β -functions at the ID location to values that are as close as possible from the S6BA-E ones. Finally, in order to reduce as much as possible the emittance, we matched the optics functions at the

center of the VADER dipoles in order to meet the TME conditions (β -functions and dispersion should be minimal). The proposed lattice including VADER dipoles is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Elettra 2.0 cell including VADER dipoles. The top plot shows the magnetic layout, with the dipole angles in blue and the quadrupolar gradient in red. The lower plot shows the evolution of the optics function throughout the lattice. The horizontal and vertical β -functions are shown with blue and orange lines respectively. The horizontal and vertical dispersion are shown with solid and dash brown lines respectively.

This proposed optics resembles the original ones in Elettra 2.0 (S6BA-E) shown in Fig.1 The dispersion is maintained to zero in the long straight sections, and the vertical β -function does not exceed 30 m in the lattice. All the quadrupoles are assumed to be powered independently - as in Elettra 2.0 - so that all the knobs can be used for the emittance optimization. All the obtained gradients are well under 100 T/m. The VADER dipole also include a quadrupolar gradient, except in the central part. This gradient should ideally be constant and equal to -23 T/m in the region where the dipole field varies, and zero in the center where the dipole field is constant.

The horizontal and vertical chromaticities are corrected to +1, as in the original lattice, using the lattice sextupoles (eight families). The obtained betatron tunes are 34.66 in the horizontal plane and 22.81 in the vertical one. At this stage of the design, the lattice octupoles are off.

Using this lattice, the equilibrium emittance is expected to be about 100 pm.rad. This gives a reduction of about 2 in comparison with the S6BA-E lattice, and a reduction factor of about 100 compared to the current Elettra ring. The beam size at the ID location is well within the Elettra 2.0 constraint since it is expected to equal to about 30 μm . Some key parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Among those parameters, one can notice a significant difference in the first order momentum compaction factor. This difference is due to the presence of strong dipoles (2.3~T peak field) in the cell. This could be a possible known issue in the future, since this would also impact the second order momentum compaction factor and therefore the Touscheck lifetime.

Parameter	S6BA-E	VADER
Hor. Emittance [pm.rad]	212	100
Ver. Emittance [pm.rad]	1	1
Beam size @ ID [μm]	60	1
Damping partition num.	1.52/1/1.48	1.53/1/1.47
Transverse tunes	33.25/9.2	34.66/22.81
Natural chromaticities	-76/-52	-158/-125
Corrected chromaticities	+1/+1	+1/+1
Compaction factor [10^{-4}]	1.2	0.54
Quadrupole gradients [T/m]	50	100

Tab. 1: Comparison of some key parameters between the S6BA-E lattice and the new VADER one.

4 Non-linear optics: dynamic aperture optimization

Before sharing the ideal profile and magnetic requirements for the VADER magnet with the magnet design team (CIEMAT), we performed a first non-linear optimization. Our observable was the Dynamic Aperture (DA) [7], which was obtained a software recently developed at CERN: XTrack [8]. When we first performed tracking simulation using the lattice proposed in Figure 5, we observed a DA that could go as low as 2 mm in the horizontal plane. This is not tolerable for a machine like Elettra that requires top-up, off-axis injection. This section therefore shows the first optimizations that were performed using XTrack. In the following, we assume the on-momentum DA, without errors.

The strategy we used (as a first step) was fairly simple: find a better working point in terms of tunes without perturbing the good emittance performance, then scan the harmonic sextupoles to try and compensate resonances that we excited by the heavy chromaticity correction, and finally scan the octupoles in order to possible recover again some DA. The tune scan results are presented in Figure 6 (left).

Every tune configuration (both horizontal and vertical tunes are being moved) corresponds to one colored line in the plot. There is not a very clear effect of the tunes on the DA, except that for some configurations that seem to enhance the DA only for some angle in the parameter space. However, our main observable remains the mean DA, and the best tune configuration was found to be (34.7, 22.845).

Using these tunes, one can then scan the harmonic sextupoles and obtain the same kind of results, that are shown now on Figure 6 (center). As for the tune scan, each colored line correspond to one harmonic sextupole configuration. In one Elettra cell, there are two families of harmonic sextupoles,

located in the dispersion free region so that they do not - or barely - affect the chromaticity. They are indeed used in order to compensate resonances that are being excited by the other magnets in the machine. The harmonic sextupoles allow the DA to reach higher values in the horizontal plane (above 5 mm) and in the vertical plane (above 2 mm). The best configuration is found for the first family powered at -30 A and the second one at 0 A. However, this is still far from the original DA foreseen for the S6BA-E lattice of Elettra 2.0 (6 mm in the horizontal plane, with errors). Our last option at the moment is to use the octupole present in the cell.

As for the harmonic sextupoles, there are two octupoles families, containing two magnets per cell each. The results of the octupoles scans are shown in Figure 6 (right). One can observe that the octupoles allow for better configurations in terms of DA, reaching 7 mm in the horizontal plane and 4 mm in the vertical one. Although including errors may further reduce the DA, it was decided to wait for the lattice implementation with the realistic magnetic design instead of the ideal one to push further the non-linear optimization.

Fig. 6 Dynamic Aperture as a function of a given tune configuration (left), harmonic sextupoles configuration (center) and octupole configuration (right).

5 Magnetic design

Specifications	CLIC DR	VADER
Magnet Gap [mm]	13	18
Max Field [T]	2.3	2.3
Transverse Gradient [T/m]	11	23
Field Quality [Units 1E-4]	≈ 1	≈ 1
Magnet Length [cm]	56	80

Tab. 2: Magnetic specification parameters for the VADER magnet as compared to the prototype built for the CLIC DRs.

The specifications for the VADER magnet are shown in Table 2, as compared to the ones of the already fabricated CLIC DRs prototype variable dipole magnet. The field profile and transverse gradient are displayed in Fig. 7. As it can be observed, the parameters are quite similar parameters

as CLIC DR in particular for the peak field of 2.3T, but VADER requires, higher transverse gradient by more than a factor of 2 (11 vs 23 T/m), but for a higher magnetic gap by around 40% (13 vs 18 mm) and a longer magnet by around 40% (56 vs 80 cm).

Fig. 7 Dipole field profile (red) and transverse gradient (blue) for the VADER magnet.

In this respect, the magnet design philosophy with respect to the CLIC DR prototype is not changed, but there is a major change in design, as shown in Fig. 8, which maintain the hyperbolic profile, but in the case VADER, they become sharper in order to achieve the required higher gradient.

Fig. 8 Pole profiles for the CLIC DR prototype (left) and the VADER magnet (right).

In contrast to the CLIC DR variable bend, which was using SmCo permanent magnet material in the variable lower-field part, the VADER magnet is designed with NdFeB permanent magnet blocks, for both low-field and high-field modules. The permanent magnet volume is increased by around 40% reaching the specified high-field peak of 2.3 T with magnet gap of 18mm (17 mm beam gap and an additional 1 mm for the vacuum chamber thickness).

Already during the design phase of the CLIC DR prototype, the feasibility of varying the magnetic field to a few % level was studied. An active trimming through coils powered by independent power convertors was discarded not only due to the design complexity but also because it defies the principle of an energy efficient magnet during operation. Instead, a passive trimming was studied and implemented by splitting the yoke in two parts and therefore allowing to adjust the magnetic circuit reluctance, which can be even used during operation with remote actuators. An improved field trimming design was implemented, with the yoke completely split in two parts supported by an aluminium block. The sliding parts achieve higher/better regulation than the CLIC DR prototype. The 3D field map of the magnet along with the simulated dipole and transverse gradient field profiles are shown in Fig. 9. The longitudinal dipole profile is achieved and closely

follows the specifications. The integrated transverse gradient exceeds actually the specifications by a few %. The field quality looks reasonable and it is in the final iteration for reducing even further multi-pole components.

Fig. 9 3D field map distribution of the VADER magnet (left), dipole (top right) and transverse gradient (bottom right) field profiles.

A sketch of the VADER magnet is presented in Fig. 10 where the three type of modules are apparent: one for the central and two for the middle and external part making a total of five.

Dimensions:
0.65 x 0.68 x 0.80 m
Weight: 1.5 T

Fig. 10 Sketch of the VADER magnet indicating the different magnet parts.

The detailed mechanical design of the three types of modules is presented in Fig. 11. Based on this, fabrication drawings are being produced. The final assembly will be based on the experience with the CLIC DR prototype.

Fig. 11 Mechanical design of the different parts of the VADER magnet.

6 Conclusion and Future Plans

A new variable bending field profile with transverse gradient is proposed and implemented for the Elettra 2.0 ring, beyond its present upgrade, following the experience with the CLIC DR longitudinally variable field demonstrator. By replacing the actual variable dipoles with peak field of 1.8 T with this new VADER magnet, with peak field of 2.3 T and hyperbolically varying field, an emittance of 100 pm is achieved, a factor of two as compared to the present design. This optics design achieves a good DA equivalent to the ones of the actual S6BA-E lattice of the Elettra 2.0 ring, after some tune, sextupole and octupole optimisation. The magnet specifications, although more challenging, they resemble the ones of the CLIC DRs demonstrator. Based on the same philosophy, the magnetic design was pursued achieving all specifications and even allowing of some improvements, with respect to the field trim capabilities. The mechanical design has been completed and drawings are being released for the final magnet fabrication and assembly at KYMA, followed by acceptance tests. The present magnetic field design will be used as input for final iterations with the optics and non-linear dynamics optimisation of the improved Elettra 2.0 lattice.

7 References

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ID	Insertion Devices
VADER	Variable Dipole for the Elettra Ring
DA	Dynamic Aperture